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SILOM AREA'S TRANSFORMATION THROUGH LGBTQ+ COMMUNITY HUB IN BANGKOK METROPOLIS

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ABSTRACT

Silom has been a dynamic urban area in Bangkok, evolved through physical, economic, and social transformations, particularly as a central LGBTQ+ hub. This research objective is to analyze the community district evolution of LGBTQ+ group in the Silom area, Bangkok Metropolis. Across six historical periods, from its early development to the present. A qualitative research methodology was employed, incorporating field observations, in-depth interviews, and document analysis.

Results reveal that Silom's physical and social structures have played crucial roles in sustaining the LGBTQ+ community, providing spaces that foster social interactions and identity expression. Additionally, urban policies, mass transit expansions, and economic growth have influenced its role as an LGBTQ+ hub. However, ongoing commercialization and economic shifts pose challenges to maintaining its unique identity. This study highlights the need for balanced urban development policies that preserve Silom's historical and cultural significance while accommodating modernization and economic progress.

Keywords: Silom, Transformation, LGBTQ+, Community hub, Bangkok

1. Statement of the Research

The formation of neighborhood identities in a large metropolis like Bangkok is the result of continuous physical, social, and cultural processes. Each neighborhood in the city has its own unique identity that reflects the historical context and economic structure of the area (Fan, Y., 2024). Although Bangkok is a city that is rapidly changing, some neighborhoods have been able to maintain their identities, such as Bang Pho, which is the center of the furniture and woodworking industry (Tumkosit, M. & Pangkesorn, A., 2024), Talad Noi, which reflects the fusion of Thai-Chinese-Portuguese cultures in a commercial context (Chimpalee, S. & Haocharoen, K., 2022), and Khao San Road, which has developed into a hub for backpacker tourism (Chusorn, S. & Atiwetin, T., 2015). Meanwhile, "Silom" has developed into an area of economic and cultural importance in Bangkok, especially as a center for the LGBTQ+ community (Duangwiset, N., 2018).

Since the 1960s, Silom has been known as an entertainment district for the gay community. In particular, during 1978–1988, there was a rapid growth of LGBTQ+ entertainment venues, with important areas such as Silom Soi 2, Silom Soi 2/1, and Silom Soi 4, which became the center of the national gay community and a source of attraction for international tourists (Watngam, T., 1999; Kotchare, T., Pathumporn, J. & Esichaikul, R., 2020). The physical characteristics of Silom, which are full of alleys and areas conducive to nighttime activities, played an important role in promoting the expression of the LGBTQ+ community. In addition, social and legal factors also helped Silom develop into an important LGBTQ+ Hub of Bangkok. For example, Songkran Silom has become an event that reflects the identity and culture of the LGBTQ+ community (Naksing, P. & Hongkananukraw, A., 2018), while the Bangkok Naruemit Pride Festival helped to reinforce Silom's role as a space for gender equality activism (Somboonkao, R., 2022). In addition, the passage of the Marriage Equality Act in 2025 played an important role in strengthening Bangkok's status. As the LGBTQ+ Rights Hub in Southeast Asia (Amending the Civil and Commercial Act B.E. 2567, 2024)

However, despite Silom's national and international significance, there is limited research on the spatial and social transformation processes of Silom. Many studies focus on the LGBTQ+ tourism industry at the national level (Liu, X. et al., 2023), lacking in-depth analysis of the factors affecting the existence and development of Silom as an LGBTQ+ Hub. This research aims to analyze the community district evolution of the LGBTQ+ Group in the Silom area, Bangkok Metropolis, by considering the factors that help this area maintain its role amidst urban changes and studying the role of the LGBTQ+ community in constructing the identity of the area. The results of the research will help enhance the understanding of the dynamics of LGBTQ+ neighborhoods in the context of an urban environment that is constantly changing.

2. Objective & Scope of Study

2.1. Objective

2.1.1 To analyze the community district evolution of LGBTQ+ Group in the Silom area, Bangkok Metropolis.

2.2. Scope of Study

This study focuses on the Silom area in Suriyawong Subdistrict, Bang Rak District, Bangkok, covering an area of 0.820 sq.km., analyzing physical factors related to LGBTQ+ activities from the mid-Rattanakosin period to the present to understand the spatial changes in terms of LGBTQ+ identity.

3. Conceptual Framework

The authors have defined the research framework based on the above objectives and the literature review. It was found that the Silom area has continuously evolved since the agricultural era until the present. This research analyzes the development of the Silom area through 6 time dimensions:

3.1 Early Silom: From Wetlands to a Business District (1851–1932)

(Mahattanobol, W., 2013)

3.2 Urban Development and Infrastructure Transformation (1932–1967)

(Bangkok Department of City Planning and Urban Development., 2021)

3.3 The Rise of the LGBTQ+ Community and Entertainment Boom (1967–1997)

(Duangwises, N., 2018)

3.4 Expansion of Public Transit and Urban Policy Impact (1997–2017)

(Charoenphol, N., 2015)

3.5 Crisis and Transformation: Pedestrianization and COVID-19 (2017–2022)

(Naksing, P., & Hongkananukraw, A., 2018)

3.6 Recognition and Advocacy for LGBTQ+ Rights (2022–Present)

(Somboonkao, R., 2022)

This study focuses on analyzing the evolution of the Silom area in physical and social dimensions. To analyze the community district evolution of LGBTQ+ Group in the Silom area, Bangkok Metropolis. which is an important destination for LGBTQ+ tourism internationally, as detailed in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Conceptual framework

Source: Authors (2025)

4. Research Methodology

The research on the Silom area's transformation through the LGBTQ+ community hub in Bangkok metropolis, Thailand is qualitative research with the following steps and details:

4.1.1 Primary data: The authors conducted the fieldwork through participatory observation, still and motion pictures, and semi-structured open-ended in-depth interviews (Photosita, C., 2021).

4.1.2 Secondary data: The authors conducted the research by searching for information from books, academic documents, research, and other related documents on 5 issues: 1) Definitions 2) Historical data of Bangkok in the Rattanakosin period (1851-2025) 3) Information about the Silom area 4) The concept of neighborhood, the formation and persistence of the neighborhood, and 5) The concept of LGBTQ groups.

4.1.3 The group of informants: was academics, architects, designers, and artists. Entrepreneurs under the organization that supports the LGBT group through specific selection (Phengsawat, W., 2008) by specifying the qualifications as those who have experience and involvement in the Silom area for 20 years or more, 1 person per group, totaling 3 people.

4.1.4 The research instrument: is a semi-structured open-ended interview form. Conduct in-depth interviews with individuals by defining the framework of the issues to be interviewed and setting questions to obtain data according to the objectives mentioned above.

4.1.5 Data collection: The authors collected data by field methods in conjunction with documents, as well as collecting data through in-depth, semi-structured, open-ended interviews.

4.1.6 Data analysis: The authors employed content analysis (Photosita, C., 2021) to examine primary data from qualified informants, integrating insights from literature, academic sources, and participatory observation, and presented the findings in an essay format to interpret the phenomena.

Figure 2 Methodology research framework
Source: Authors (2025)

5. Result

5.1.1 History of Silom District

Silom area began with physical development during the reign of King Rama IV (1804-1868) to accommodate foreigners before becoming an agricultural area for the nobility and the wealthy and was influenced by globalization (Angsuwatthana, S., 2009). The growth of businesses and changes in land structure led to the development of an important economic district, especially after World War II (Sri-udom, O., 1992).

The designation of Silom as a commercial area in 1957 (Ronghanam, P., 2015) and the development of the city's business and technology center (Pattanaanek, W., 2000) led to the continuous growth of Silom. Important factors include the introduction of mass transit systems such as the BTS Skytrain in 1999 (Bangkok Mass Transit System Public Company Limited., 2024) and the MRT in 2004 (Bangkok Expressway and Metro Public Company Limited., 2024). To this day, Silom remains an important commercial center of Bangkok. Reflecting the economic and social development of the city (Office of Urban Planning & Development., 2024)

Figure 3 (a) Land use zoning from the Bangkok City Plan (2013), showing a formal spatial structure in Bang Rak District
 (b) Local map of Silom, indicating actual community landmarks and usage zones based on field survey and site observation

Source: Department of City Planning and Urban Development, BMA (2025)

5.1.2 Time Series of Silom's Area Development

The development of Silom can be traced through six key periods, starting from its origins as agricultural land under King Rama IV to its transformation into a key business district. Over time, Silom evolved into a hub for LGBTQ+ culture and entertainment, driven by both infrastructure developments like mass transit and social changes. Despite challenges, including the impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic and commercialization, Silom continues to be a significant center for both business and LGBTQ+ identity.

(1) Early Silom: From Wetlands to a Business District (1851–1932)

Silom area originated during the reign of King Rama IV when foreigners who came to work in the capital experienced health problems due to the lack of western-style horseback riding roads in Bangkok. He ordered Chaophraya Srisuriyawong to dig Khlong Bang Khwang from Bang Rak to Khlong Thanon Trong. As a result, the surrounding area began to develop and the new road was called “Thanon Khwang” (Angsuwatthana, S., 2009). Before the development, most of the Silom area was agricultural land under the ownership of nobles and wealthy people, such as the rice fields of Chaophraya Surasakmontri (Chiem Saeng-Chuto) in the Sala Daeng area and the vegetable garden of Princess Krom Luang Saphasart Suphakitch. However, when foreigners installed Silom machines in this area, Thanon Khwang began to be called “Thanon Silom”, although it is not clear when this name came about. However, according to the records of S. Phlai Noi, Silom Road appeared in the document of the royal route of King Chulalongkorn (Rama V) on July 16, 1891, which shows that this name already existed before that (Angsuwatthana, S., 2009).

In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, Silom transitioned from an agricultural area to a residential and commercial hub. The influx of the foreign community in Bangkok led to infrastructure developments, including road construction and the establishment of commercial buildings. Noble lands, like those of Chao Phraya Surasakmontri, were divided for private use, with some areas being developed into residential houses and institutions like St. Joseph Convent School. Soi Phiphat, originally owned by Phraya Phiphat Kosa, was developed to connect surrounding areas, becoming one of the busiest alleys in Bangkok.

By 1932, Silom had evolved into a key economic area, hosting businesses involved in international trade, printing, and various shops along the road. This marked a shift in Bangkok's landscape from an agricultural base to a commercial and business center shaped by globalization. (Sri-udom, O., 1992).

(2) Urban Development and Infrastructure Transformation (1932–1967)

Between 1932 and 1967, Silom underwent significant urban development and infrastructure changes, evolving from an agricultural area into Bangkok's leading commercial and economic hub. In 1957, Bangkok's urban planning officially designated Silom as the Central Business District (CBD), which spurred widespread real estate development, office building growth, and the expansion of multinational corporations, banks, and financial centers, cementing Silom's status as a key economic district.

In addition to its commercial growth during the day, Silom has also become a major hub for nightlife, particularly in areas like Patpong, which was influenced by the presence of American military personnel during the Vietnam War. The rise of bars and nightclubs created spaces for the LGBTQ+ community in secret and promoted their identity within the area. These infrastructure changes not only strengthened Silom's role as Bangkok's business hub but also inadvertently created spaces for LGBTQ+ social interaction and cultural expression, laying the foundation for Silom's future as a diverse and prominent nightlife hub.

(3) The Rise of the LGBTQ+ Community and Entertainment Boom (1967–1997)

The emergence of LGBTQ+ spaces in Silom reflects the gradual process of space development and identity formation of the LGBTQ+ community from 1967–1997. In particular, the Patpong area has become an important central initiative for the LGBTQ+ community in Bangkok and has continued to expand to Silom. This area has continuously developed from a space that was never designed to accommodate the LGBTQ+ group but has been transformed into a space that responds to the needs of this group through social and cultural processes. These changes are not the result of specific planning, but rather the dynamics of society that are open to and supportive of diverse gender expressions and identities (Peelasi, W., 2014; Duangwiset, N., 2018).

Figure 4 Reconstructed map of Patpong Road (Silom), based on archival records and present-day fieldwork, showing the emergence of LGBTQ+ spaces between 1967 and 1997

Source: Authors (2024)

During the night time when social restrictions are not strict, the LGBTQ+ community in Silom can express themselves safely. This area has become a place where LGBTQ+ people can express their identity without fear of being rejected by outside society. Although the places in Silom were not designed specifically to accommodate the LGBTQ+ group at first, the adaptation of the area and word of mouth have made Silom a place that reflects the construction of identity and gender expression, such as the complex traffic routes within the area that facilitate the interaction of LGBTQ+ people (Peelasi, W., 2014). In 1966, gay-specific entertainment venues were opened in the Silom area, such as 99, Siamese, Garage, and Rome Club. The emergence of these entertainment venues represents the integration of the LGBTQ+ community in Silom. During 1978–1988, the gay entertainment business in Silom grew rapidly, with more than 20 gay entertainment venues, such as Super Star, Harry, and Krua Silom, indicating the expansion of the LGBTQ+ area and its more systematic integration. There is also the Gay Sauna business that helps to promote the growth of the LGBTQ+ circle (Duangwiset, N., 2018).

Informant 1 mentioned the changes that occurred in the Silom area, which were caused by the process of urban and social development that made the Silom area more open to the LGBTQ+ group without the need for specific design, but were caused by the social dynamics that resulted in Silom area becoming a center for the expression of sexuality and identity of the LGBTQ+ group in a meaningful way. The emergence of the activity of "**Bar Hopping**", which is traveling from one bar to another during the night, also played an important role in the development of the LGBTQ+ community in the Silom area. This activity reflects the creation of interactions among people in the LGBTQ+ community and the systematic networking of the

LGBTQ+ group. Informant 3 confirmed that **"Silom is a connection point for activities in the LGBTQ+ group."**

From the perspective of Informant 1, Silom is not only a space for sexual expression but also an important space for creating identity and social acceptance. The development of LGBTQ+ areas in the Silom area reflects the growth of the LGBTQ+ community that occurred from the gradual development of the city and society without the need for specific design. However, it comes from the adaptation of the area to respond to the needs of the LGBTQ+ group and promote Silom as an area that plays an important role in shaping the identity and sexual expression of the LGBTQ+ group.

(4) Expansion of Public Transit and Urban Policy Impact (1997–2017)

The development of the Silom area from 1997–2017 has been significantly changed by both infrastructure factors and urban policies. The opening of the BTS Skytrain in 1999 (Bangkok Mass Transit System Public Company Limited, 2024) and the MRT subway in 2004 (Bangkok Expressway and Metro Public Company Limited, 2024) have made the area more accessible, resulting in Silom remaining as Bangkok's central business district (CBD) (Office of Urban Planning and Development., 2024) and attracting investment from the business sector, especially in the tourism and LGBTQ+ entertainment industries.

In the early 2000s, Silom remained a hub for the LGBTQ+ community, with landmarks such as DJ Station, Freeman Dance Arena, and Silom Plaza, areas that attracted both Thai and international visitors. Informant 3 stated, **"Silom used to be a paradise for LGBTQ+ nightlife, with bars and entertainment venues open until the early hours, where everyone could express themselves freely."** However, the expansion of mass transit and changes in urban policies have led to the structure of the area starting to change.

Informant 1 explained that after the 1997 economic crisis, the government began to control the nightlife business more, resulting in restrictions on the opening and closing hours of entertainment venues, which caused Silom to lose its role as a nightlife area open to the LGBTQ+ community. In addition, the rise of internet technology in the early 2000s gave LGBTQ+ people an alternative to meeting online instead of using traditional physical spaces. This caused many entertainment venues to close down or change their format to accommodate foreign tourists instead.

The first informant continued to say that Although Silom is facing changes in the business sector and urban policy, the government is still trying to preserve the area's centrality through the Silom Walking Street Project 2010, which was organized to stimulate the economy and promote cultural tourism. The idea was to transform Silom Road into a pedestrian and nightlife area that attracted Thai and international tourists. However, the project began to slow down in 2019 due to competition from other tourist attractions in Bangkok and changes in consumer behavior towards online platforms.

The changes in Silom from 1997–2017 had both positive and negative effects. In terms of positives, the development of mass transit systems has made traveling to Silom more convenient. As a result, the area has become a major business and tourism hub, attracting foreign investors and tourists, and boosting the area's economy. Meanwhile, changes in media and technology have given LGBTQ+ people more options to network and meet, without relying solely on physical venues.

However, Informant 2 explained that these changes have had negative impacts, especially the decline of LGBTQ+ entertainment venues, which have been gradually replaced by large commercial businesses, causing Silom's identity as an LGBTQ+ hub to gradually fade, in line with Informant 1 and 3. Informant 1 also explained that stricter government regulations, such as restrictions on entertainment venues' opening and closing hours and measures to control

street-side trading areas, have reduced the area's liveliness at night. In addition, higher costs for using space have made it difficult for small businesses and local communities to operate and compete with large capital groups. Although these changes have brought economic prosperity, they have also come with challenges that have caused Silom to lose some of its former identity, resulting in the gradual decline of the LGBTQ+ community's identity in this area. Increasingly commercialized urban development has changed Silom significantly between 1997–2017.

(5) Crisis and Transformation: Pedestrianization and COVID-19 (2017–2022)

Figure 5 Atmosphere of Silom area during the COVID-19 pandemic situation

Source: Authors (2024)

Although Silom has been hit hard by the COVID-19 pandemic, which has severely impacted businesses, especially entertainment venues, shops, and services related to the LGBTQ+ community, which have inevitably closed or downsized their businesses, Silom, with its unique physical, historical, and cultural factors, still has the potential to recover and return to being a hub for nightlife activities once the situation improves.

Throughout the COVID-19 pandemic, Silom has undergone a sudden structural change, from the closure of establishments that used to be landmarks for the LGBTQ+ community to a greater reliance on online channels, which has reduced the importance of the physical space compared to the previous era. However, such changes do not mean that Silom has completely lost its original identity, but rather, it has adapted to a new context where technology and consumer behavior have become more important.

Although the COVID-19 pandemic has significantly impacted Silom, at the same time, it has accelerated the area's transformation into a new context that combines traditional businesses with digital platforms. After the pandemic, Silom is not just an entertainment and nightlife district, but also reflects the LGBTQ+ community's adaptation process under an urban environment that is changing with economic and social dynamics.

According to the author's survey, it was found that the group of buildings that used to be entertainment venues in the Silom area have changed their utility by still using the original building structure but have been converted into restaurants or general shops to be able to continue their business amidst the high rent burden in the central business district. However, some businesses have completely changed their space usage patterns, such as developing condominium projects, hotels, or department stores. From interviews with 3 informants, it was found that there was a consistent opinion that Silom is still an area that is of interest to investors and large capital groups. Although some places that used to be gathering places for night owls in the past have changed their usage, Silom's image as a nightlife district, especially as an important LGBTQ+ community of Bangkok, has remained from the past to the present.

(6) Recognition and Advocacy for LGBTQ+ Rights (2022–Present)

Thailand has seen significant progress in LGBTQ+ rights and acceptance since 2022, particularly in terms of legal advances related to LGBTQ+ rights, the drive for same-sex marriage, and Silom's role as a hub for the LGBTQ+ community.

Silom has remained a symbol of Thailand's LGBTQ+ community for nearly six decades, and in recent years, social and legal changes have helped the area grow once again. After the COVID-19 situation eased, Thailand has undergone significant changes, particularly in the demands for gender equality and rights, which was reflected in the 2022 Bangkok Naruemit Pride festival held in Silom.

According to Informant 1, Silom used to be an area that provided opportunities for Thais to become entrepreneurs within the area. However, in recent years, changes in business and investment from foreign investors have resulted in many Thais becoming mere service users or employees in the area rather than business owners as in the past, which has reduced the sense of belonging and ownership of the area among Thais, which may result in Silom being a **"legendary story"** for the previous generation rather than a living and economically significant area today.

On the other hand, Informant 2 viewed Silom as still an important area for the LGBTQ+ community, due to historical reasons, the context of the area, and the sense of togetherness that continues to be conveyed through social networks and various activities. Although the area is facing physical and economic changes, its existence helps generate economic circulation not only in the entertainment sector, but also in other business sectors such as restaurants, hotels, and transportation services.

The third informant emphasized the importance of Silom as an area that promotes the rights and freedoms of the LGBTQ+ group, which should be systematically developed, especially by using symbols that reflect the identity of the community, such as the rainbow flag, architectural design, and urban landscape, to make this area a true LGBTQ+ tourism and cultural destination, not just a nighttime entertainment area.

The fact that Thailand is the first country in Southeast Asia to pass the law on marriage equality, which will be effective in January 2025, strengthens the country's image as an LGBTQ+ hub and helps stimulate the tourism economy, especially in the Silom area. Since 2024-2025, Silom has seen the opening of more than 5 gay entertainment venues, such as BEEF and Silver Sand in Silom Soi 4, Rush in Silom Soi 2/1, and the important area of Silom Soi 2, where DJ Station remains the main hub. Nearby entertainment venues include Him in Thaniya and Cell in Silom Soi 5, as well as the emergence of gay entertainment venues inside Silom Edge, a 24-hour shopping mall.

Despite progress in many areas, challenges remain, especially economic changes that have forced the LGBTQ+ community in Silom to adapt to capital and tourism trends. Informant 2 and Informant 3 agree that without a systematic development plan, Silom may become just a commercial area that lacks cultural meaning, which will affect the identity of the LGBTQ+ community in the long run.

Ultimately, Silom remains an important area for the LGBTQ+ community in Thailand, but it is facing economic, social, and legal changes. If it can be developed into an area that truly reflects LGBTQ+ identity, and receives support from the government and private sectors to promote the rights and economic opportunities of the LGBTQ+ community, it will be able to maintain Silom's role as Asia's LGBTQ+ hub.

6. Discussion

The results of the study indicate that Silom has successfully maintained its identity despite ongoing urban transformations, aligning with Fan's (2024) idea that urban communities shape their identity through continuous physical and social processes. As an **Entertainment Area**, Silom remains a key nightlife destination, especially for the LGBTQ+ community, though some venues have declined due to urban development and the influx of large capital investors.

The presence of LGBTQ+ spaces is deeply rooted in **Symbolic Activities**, both overt and subtle, such as public events, gatherings, and designated venues that foster community interaction. This aligns with Duangwiset (2018), who highlighted the role of nightlife in creating safe spaces for LGBTQ+ groups. However, economic and urban policy changes since the late 1990s have led to a gradual decline in LGBTQ+ entertainment venues, supporting Liu et al. (2023)'s argument that commercial transformations can impact the identity of areas once central to LGBTQ+ communities.

These changes have also affected the LGBTQ+ **Sense of Place** in Silom, as spaces once considered safe zones are being replaced by commercial developments that cater more to investors than to the original community. While Silom remains a major LGBTQ+ tourist destination, its social landscape has shifted from what it once was. Furthermore, the rise of online platforms has led to a migration of social activities to digital spaces, differing from Peelasi (2014), who primarily emphasized the role of physical locations in shaping LGBTQ+ interactions.

These transformations are not only reflected in lived experiences, but also captured through spatial and temporal patterns identified in the field. Although limited in space, the visual materials included in this study derive from such patterns and serve as analytical representations of how Silom has evolved through overlapping uses and identity-based practices.

Although the passage of the **Civil and Commercial Act B.E. 2567 (2024)** has reinforced Silom's status as an LGBTQ+ hub, ongoing challenges such as economic shifts and commercial development remain factors that could erode its traditional identity in the future. This underscores the need for policies that preserve the district's cultural identity while ensuring balanced urban development.

7. Conclusion

This study examines the transformation of Silom from both physical and social perspectives, emphasizing its role as a significant **LGBTQ+ community hub** in Bangkok. The findings reveal that Silom has undergone continuous evolution since the 19th century, which can be categorized into six key periods.

The primary objective of this research is to analyze the evolution of the LGBTQ+ community district in the Silom area and to explore the factors that have allowed it to persist despite urban transformations. The results indicate that Silom's physical and social development is deeply intertwined with Bangkok's broader urbanization process, particularly the effects of mass transit expansion, urban policies, and digital technology. While Silom remains a key **LGBTQ+ hub**, economic and social shifts—such as the decline of LGBTQ+ entertainment venues, the rise of digital social spaces, and the influx of large corporate investments are altering its identity, which aligns with Liu et al. (2023) regarding the impact of commercial transformations on historically LGBTQ+-centered districts.

Additionally, this study highlights that Silom's **unique urban layout**, characterized by intricate alleys and diverse public spaces, has historically fostered LGBTQ+ social activities and identity formation. However, as the city's **entertainment landscape shifts from physical venues to digital platforms**, the traditional **sense of place** for LGBTQ+ groups is evolving.

This suggests that the preservation of Silom's identity should be an integral part of urban development policies that balance economic growth with cultural and historical significance.

This research fills a critical knowledge gap by contextualizing the transformation of Silom as an LGBTQ+ Community Hub and provides insights into the future of urban policies that can sustain diverse social identities in rapidly changing metropolitan environments. Moving forward, maintaining **Silom's legacy as an inclusive space** requires policy interventions that recognize its **historical role**, its **cultural significance**, and its **ongoing contributions to LGBTQ+ representation in Bangkok**.

The transformation of Silom, as shaped by overlapping spatial practices and identity-based uses, may be understood through the emerging concept of a Constructed Multi-functional Identity-based District (CMID) a tentative framework currently under development by the author to explore how spatial identity can be formed without permanent settlement, through sustained social and symbolic use. Its full articulation will be examined further in the author's ongoing doctoral research.

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